

Answer all questions in the answer booklet provided.

QUESTION ONE

A 32-year-old woman with 38 weeks' gestation is scheduled for emergency caesarean. There is the possibility of developing Mendelson's syndrome because the client ate rice an hour ago.

- a.
 - i. What is Mendelson syndrome? - 2marks
 - ii. State **FOUR (4)** methods of preventing Mendelson syndrome in a patient schedule for emergency caesarean section. - 4marks
- b. How do you manage a patient at the labour ward with diagnosis of eclampsia? - 8 marks
- c. Outline **SIX (6)** obstetrics emergencies that needs immediate interventions - 6marks

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Fobi is admitted to the theater for salpingectomy. as the scrub nurse for the procedure, you are to assist in skin preparation and draping;

- a. Describe the procedure for surgical skin preparation - 5marks
- b. Mention **THREE (3)** antiseptic solution used in skin preparation and their action - 3marks
- c. Outline **FOUR (4)** properties of antiseptic solutions - 4marks
- d. State **THREE (3)** purpose of skin preparation - 3marks
- e. Enumerate **FIVE (5)** characteristics of a drape - 5marks

MS. REGINA ACQUAH